

The Issues of Effectiveness of Advertisement Communication Process: A Case Study of Lithuania Consumers

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Abstract—The goal of this study was to disclose the core of the advertising research based on the psychological aspects by acquainting with the nature of advertising research and revealing the importance of psychological aspects of advertising during the advertising research. The growing interest in consumer response to advertisement served as an encouragement to make the analysis of psychological aspects of the advertising research, because the information obtained during the advertising research helps to answer the question how advertising really works. In the research analysis focuses on the nature of advertising research. The place of advertising research in advertisement planning process and the advertising research process are unfolded. Moreover, the importance of psychological aspects in the advertising research is being examined. The certain psychological aspects like the particularities of advertising communication process, psychological process that are active at advertising acceptance and awareness process as well as the advertising effects are analysed in more detail.

Keywords—Advertising, communication process, advertising message, advertising psychology.

I. CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

WE may treat the advertisement from two perspectives: as advertisement specialists and consumers. Advertisement specialists make decisions incident to planning, creation and conveying of the advertisement. Consumers, on the contrary, react to the advert which advertisement specialists have created and presented them. After incorporating these two perspectives we can state that constant interaction of advert and consumer is observed in the advertisement process. As marketing specialists transfer particular message to the consumers while advertise something, the advertisement may be called communication process.

It should be noticed that transferring message in the advertisement various elements – such as words, views, colours, music and so on - are used. While creating the advert, advertisement specialists must measure how every of these elements will influence the consumer because consumers' reaction to the advert will depend namely on the common operation of these elements. Knowing how communication process operates during the advertisement we may notice how the advert influences the consumer and, taking it into consideration, to carry out properly advertising researches seeking to increase the effectiveness of the advertisement. The advertisement is not ordinary

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communication process as during it flow of information goes only into one direction.

Wilkie separates advertisement communication process into six stages. He assigns three of them to the sender of information, i.e. advertisement specialist, and assigns the rest three ones to the receiver of the information, i.e. consumer [12] (Fig. 1).

At the first stage of the advertising communication process advertisement specialist settles the goal of the advertising campaign. Scholten and Wilkie say that the most often goals of the advertisement are he following [10], [12]:

- *persuasion*, for example, intention to persuade consumers that advertised product is better than product proposed by competitors;
- *reinforcement*, for example, to aid consumers to evaluate a product favourably after it was obtained;
- *reminder*, for example, to evoke favourable remembrances about the product;
- *acceleration of purchasing*, for example, to encourage consumer to obtain the product as quickly as possible.

When advertisement goals are settled the first gap emerges in the communication process: if *the planned goals are not accessible*. This may happen either if the goals are unreal or formulated confusedly or if selected advertisement strategy does not fit to reach the planned goals.

At the second stage of communication process advertisement specialist starts to plan advertising campaign. He / she must encode the information which should be delivered to the consumer, i.e. he / she must decide what message to deliver to consumer. It is purposeful to carry out *idea researches* at this stage seeking to formulate as effective as possible message.

If *message which is planned to deliver is selected incorrectly*, the second gap evokes in the communication process. As we have already mentioned, idea research may help to avoid this mistake [4].

At the third stage of communication process advertisement specialist (sender) sends the information. But, before sending the message it should be decided which advertisement means should be chosen in order to deliver this message to consumer (receiver), i. e. the advert must be created. Most often advertising agencies do it. As we have already mention before, while preparing the advert it necessary to decide what exactly words will be used, what will be represent in the advert, what colours will be used, what music and so on. Information found out investigating *communication* and *copy* may help advertisement specialists to make more effective decisions at this stage of advertisement communication process.

While conveying the advert to the consumer to which advertisement specialist wants to convey it, the third gap of advertisement communication process may be observed, which evokes *due to technical obstacles during the convey of the advert*. Wilkie calls technical obstacles – such as interruption of TV broadcasting, wrong colours of the published advert and so on – as *noise* which disturbs correct convey of the advert to the consumer [12].

effective when there is an accordance between the first stage – the goal of the advertising campaign – and the sixth stage – consumer's behaviour, between the second stage – encoding of information – and the fifth stage – recoding of information, between the third stage – sending of information – and the fourth stage – reception of the advert.

II. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES AND METHOD

As it was already mentioned before we may treat advertisement as a communication process because creators of the advert transfer certain message about a product to consumers. Actors of the market seek that the advertisement would be effective i. e. would arouse desirable reaction of the consumers. We may affirm that just effective communication may ensure effectiveness of the advertisement. Advertisement communication process will be successful when accordance will be between the goal of advertisement campaign and consumers' behaviour, encoding and recoding information, sending and receiving of the advert. Advertising researches enable to find out if the mentioned accordance is inherent to advertisement communication process.

Problem of this research involves necessity to check out the accordance between sending and receiving the advertisement. It enables to go deeper into the particularities of sending and receiving the advertisement and gives more information about advertisement communication process.

We have chosen the advertisement of such product which authors and representatives of the target auditorium we are able to interrogate. We have decided to check effectiveness of the communication process of advertisement of "Kvietinis baltas" ("Wheaten white") beer produced by JSC "Gubernija". Employers of advertising agency MAP who created this advertisement agreed to take part in the research. As beer is a product of prompt usage, impulsive purchase, a lot of young people use it consequently it was convenient to interrogate representatives of the target segment of "Kvietinis baltas" beer

Research question – *What is effectiveness of advertisement communication process of "Kvietinis baltas" beer in accordance's between sending and receiving the advertisement aspects when consumers of 18 – 30 years old are the target audience?*

Hypotheses

Performed analysis of the literature enables us to formulate the following *hypotheses*:

- H1:** *A person perceives product brand personality in an advertisement equally irrespective if he / she is a sender or receiver of an advertisement in an advertisement communication process.*
- H2:** *The representatives of different genders perceive product brand personality in an advertisement differently.*
- H3:** *The information that people learn about a product brand personality during an advertisement communication process depends on if people use a product (and how often they use it) and if people do not use it at all.*

We have formulated the following *tasks* in order to check hypotheses:

- 1) To examine how consumers of 18 – 30 years

Fig. 1 The stages of the advertisement communication process [12]

At the fourth stage of the communication process consumer receives the advert which is conveyed to him / her by the particular carrier. Psychic process - *perception* – is very important during the receiving process. In case if *receiving and perceiving the advert particular problems rise*, the fourth gap is observed in the advertisement communication process. A consumer must understand language and symbols used in an advert thus the consumer will be able to receive advertising information precisely when his / her *cognitive skills* will make it possible to receive and process received information properly [5]. Consumer's *motivation* is very important factor, too.

At the fifth stage information received by the consumer is recoded. Vakratsas and Ambler state, that at this stage (which they call intermediate between reception of the advert and behaviour of the consumer) "consciously or unconsciously the advert must arouse such psychical phenomena's as *thinking, feelings and remembrances* about earlier purchasing, usage and advert of the product". If the consumer *does not retain the message send by the advert* or can not reproduce favourable impression about the product which was formed by advert, the gap is observed in the communication process after the fifth stage [1], [11].

At the sixth stage of the advertising communication process consumer behaviour which has been encouraged by the advert is observed. That may be choice, usage of the product, loyalty to the product and so on.

According to [12], from the point of view of advertisement specialist advertising communication process

old perceive product brand personality in the advert of "Kvietinis baltas" beer;

- 2) To determine what authors wanted to say about the product brand personality in the advert of "Kvietinis baltas" beer;
- 3) To find out if consumers of 18 – 30 years old of different genders perceive the product brand personality in the advert of "Kvietinis baltas" beer differently;
- 4) To find out if consumers of 18 – 30 years old whom distinguish themselves with different behavioural peculiarities (use / do not use beer; if use – how often do it; like / dislike novelties) perceive the product brand personality in the advert of "Kvietinis baltas" beer differently.

In order to formulate objective conclusions regarding investigated respondents we have chosen *quantitative research*. We wanted to present got findings in digital form and it is easier to do it then quantitative but not qualitative research is performed.

During the research according as consumers perceive the product brand personality researchers judge about the effectiveness of advertisement communication process in aspect of sending and receiving the advert. To our mind survey as method of data's selection is the best for this research. We were able to interrogate a lot of respondents and formulate objective conclusions from the collected data because performing the research respondents were asked to fill in the questionnaire in writing.

Questionnaire consisted of two parts. In the first part respondent was asked to rate how 39 characteristics of the personality fit for the "Kvietinis baltas" beer (produced by JSC "Gubernija".) in the advert (it was presented them, too). We have used a Likert scale from 1 to 5 for the rating, where 1 means "does not fit at all" and 5 – "fits very much".

At the beginning of the second part the respondent was asked if he / she remembers the mentioned advert of "Kvietinis" beer. The aim of this question was to find out if respondents recognize this advert. Also questions about the respondent – his / her age, gender, attitude to novelties and usage of beer - were in this part of the questionnaire.

Respondents were selected using non-random sampling method. When we selected respondents it was important to select men and women, of 18 – 30 years old, who drink and do not drink beer. Distribution of respondents according to gender and frequency of using beer is presented in Table I.

	I can not answer	9	1	10
	Total (drink beer)	106	32	138
	Total:	138	40	178

Also we have interrogated four employees of MAP advertising agency.

In order to process quantitative data of the research we have used *SPSS (version 12.0) packet*. We have systematized data using descriptive statistics, arithmetic average, standard deviation, and confidence interval. In order to compare answers regarding the gender and beer's usage we have calculated Student criterion (*t-test*).

In order the research would distinguish itself with internal validity we used scale of characteristics of product brand personality (formulated earlier and used by other authors) in the questionnaire. Author of this scale J. L. Aaker (1997) states that it is valid and it possible to generalise data collected regarding this scale.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As well as author of scale of characteristics of product brand personality J. L. Aaker (1997) we wanted to get more clear data and for this purpose we summarised characteristics of product brand personality to 15 characteristics of personality (*practical, fair, useful, fun, brave, gallant, imaginative, modern, reliable, understanding, successful, aristocratic, charming, wild, strict*) and them - to 5 dimensions of the personality (*heartiness, excitation / excitement, competence, delicacy, severity / roughness*).

Results of the research showed that investigated persons of 18 – 30 years old think that regarding to presented advert of "Kvietinis baltas" beer the characteristic of product brand personality *real* is the best for this brand of beer (average 3,6461). As well we should notice that standard deviation of characteristic *real* is the smallest (1,0962) and reliable interval is narrowest [3,4839; 3,8082] consequently opinions of interrogated persons rating this characteristic of product brand personality coincided most of all. Characteristic *rough* fits to this brand least (average 2,0112). Standard deviations are the highest and reliable intervals are the widest of two characteristics of product brand personality – *western* and *ultra-fashion*. We may think that interrogated persons interpreted these characteristics of product brand personality rather differently thus their opinions about the question if these characteristics of the product brand personality are inherent to "Kvietinis baltas" beer have not coincided.

Authors of the advert think that these characteristics of the product brand personality – *hearty, real, useful, fun and friendly* (averages of all 4,2500) – fit to "Kvietinis baltas" beer. As we can see the listed characteristics involve the characteristic *real*, which was rated by the respondents of 18 – 30 years old as the best for this brand of beer.

Comparing ratings of "Kvietinis baltas" beer brand personality made by receivers of the advert (respondents of 18 – 30 years old) and senders of the advert (authors) we have performed the analysis on the basis of ratings of 15 characteristics of the personality. According to ratings of characteristics of mentioned beer's brand personality presented by authors of the advert and respondents of 18 – 30 years old we may state that in spite of there is some

TABLE I

DISTRIBUTION OF RESPONDENTS ACCORDING TO GENDER AND FREQUENCY OF BEER'S USAGE

Usage of beer		Gender		Total
		Female	Male	
Do not drink beer		32	8	40
Drink beer	More often then one time per week	13	14	27
	one time per week	19	7	26
	2-3 times per moth	31	6	37
	One time per month	19	3	22
	More seldom	15	1	16

differences between ratings of characteristics of product brand personality made by receivers of the advert and senders of the advert. However, **total profile of product brand personality is rather similar**. Ratings made by senders of the advert are a little bit higher except of the following characteristics of product brand personality: *brave, modern, wild, and strict*. As it is common to treat the characteristics *wild* and *strict* as undesirable (“bad”) we have expected that senders of the advert would rate these characteristics of product brand personality as less inherent than receivers of the advert would do. However, these assumptions were not proved and this may mean that authors of the advert estimated the advert created by them rather objective.

According to data of the research we may say that receivers and senders of the advert rate six characteristics of the product brand personality – *strict, wild, charming, brave, aristocratic, successful* – similarly. Rating of these five characteristics – *understanding, fun, useful, honest and trustable* – differ most of all.

Generalising accomplished analysis of data we may say that *perception of product brand personality in the advertisement depends on who is the person in advertisement communication process – sender or receiver of advertisement*. Consequently **the first hypothesis has not proved out**.

Checking if representatives of different genders perceive product brand personality in advertisement differently we have compared averages of the groups by Student criterion. Representatives of different genders rate these characteristics of product brand personality statistically reliably: *reliable* ($t=2,054, p<0,05$) and *successful* ($t=2,119, p<0,05$). Women more often than men think that such characteristics of product brand personality as *reliable* (averages respectively $3,2238 > 2,8667$) and *successful* (averages respectively $3,2126 > 2,8083$) are inherent to personality of “Kvietinis baltas” beer. As competence dimension joins these two characteristics, ratings of competence made by women and men differ statistically reliably ($t=2,061, p<0,05$).

The second hypothesis proved out partly: representatives of different genders perceive some characteristics of product brand personality in advert differently and perceive some characteristics similarly.

The third hypothesis - if the information that people learn about a product brand personality during an advertisement communication process depends on if people use a product (and how often they use it) and if people do not use it at all – has not proved out. Statistically reliable different neither between answers of those respondents who drink beer and do not drink beer, nor between answer of those who drink beer unequally often was not found.

Seeking to say if communication process of advertisement of “Kvietinis baltas” beer in aspect of sending and receiving the advert was successful one should base on ratings of “Kvietinis alus” beer brand personality made by authors and receivers of the advert. We have already done it. After analysis we conclude that in spite of there is some differences between ratings of product brand personality made by authors and receivers of the advert, the whole profile of product brand personality is similar. This shows that *advertisement specialists managed to transfer*

desirable knowledge about “Kvietinis baltas” beer to receivers of the advert during advertisement communication process. The fact that even 71 (39.9 percent) respondents recognise (strictly speaking – reproduce) this advert, unless it was conveyed them through advertisement carriers approximately one and a half years ago proves that advertisement communication process was successful.

IV. CONCLUSION AND AREAS OF FURTHER RESEARCH

Topicality of analysis of psychological aspects of advertising research is revealed, nature of advertising research is discussed, is gone deep into importance of psychological aspects of advertisement carrying out advertising researches in this study and regarding to theoretical decisions quantitative research of psychological aspects of advertising researches is performed and its findings are described in this study. Generalising accomplished analysis of data we may say that perception of product brand personality in the advertisement depends on who is the person in advertisement communication process – sender or receiver of advertisement. Analysis and quantitative research carried out in this study inspire performance of other advertising researches. First of all it would be worth to go deeper into psychological aspects of beer advertisement in order to find out which remedy is best from the mentioned ones for beer advertisement seeking to arouse affect’s and experience’s psychological effects. Secondly, it would be worth to observe how perception of product brand personality changes over time and estimate influence of such factors as carriers of advertisement, budget of advertisement, advertising catchword and others to perception of product brand.

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